

Camel Figure in Seljuk Period Ceramic Art

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Camel Figure in Seljuk Period Ceramic Art

Abstract

The camel figure that emerged in Seljuk porcelain art and geography will be covered in this essay. Our study primarily focuses on analyzing the composition, subject, and shape of camel figure examples in ceramics, in addition to analyzing the figure from a symbolic standpoint.

Despite being associated with Arab culture, the camel gradually found a home in Turkish society and began to be understood and assigned significance in relation to certain cultural icons. Camels were associated with the sky element in Turkish art, and camels—especially male camels—were regarded as appropriate (Çoruhlu, 2014: 217). Under the influence of the totemism belief system, camels were seen as a lucky or happy emblem in the early eras of Turkish mythology, along with many other animals. Like the males of other animals, male camels, referred to as "buğra," were deemed substantial by the heroes (Çoruhlu, 2002: 146).

It has been said that the camel represented communication between the people and the state in the Seljuk and Ottoman eras of ancient Turkey (Ögel, 1995: 538). During the Ottoman Empire, camels were widely utilized for food, sports, the military, and economic endeavors. The camel served as a valuable pack animal in ancient armies, much like the horse did in

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warfare and as a cavalry animal. Because of this, the state historically placed a high value on camel breeding (Yarkin, 1965: 100).

During the Seljuk era, camels were frequently featured in Turkish-Islamic art. The camel may be seen incorporated into designs on metal objects, pottery, tiles, and, most notably, miniatures. Ceramic materials gave the camel motif, which is prevalent in artwork from the Seljuk period, new significance. It was positioned inside a certain theme in the historical artworks. Among these topics, Behram Gur and Azade are the ones that stand out and contribute meaning to ceramic art. The composition of Behrâm-ı Gûr and his beloved concubine Azade, with storytelling on camel back and similar modifications, is a composition that is often utilized in pottery works.

Key Words: *Ceramics, Camel, Seljuk*

CAMEL FIGURE IN SELJUK PERIOD CERAMIC ART

The piece is a slanted-mouthed, high-based jug with a single handle. The jug's outside is embellished with an opaque white glazed minai technique. The lips are surrounded by a wavy blue line. Once more, a blue-glazed Kufi calligraphy band with separate pieces on a white backdrop encircles the lips. It says on the writing band that a well-being prayer was said. On the interior of the jug's rim, a dakufi writing band is visible. The composition is positioned in between the neck's red surround and the body's blue border.

There is a figure on the body and three camels of various colors. The corpse is surrounded by a row of camels. Sitting is Figürbağdaş's posture. He's dressed in a green, six-sleeved costume with stars on it. He has shoulder-length black hair. On his head, he has a red-black hat. The figure features a nose, a tiny mouth, big almond eyes, and eyebrows that resemble bows.

The brown camel with two humps is the one positioned first on the body. You cannot see the camel's neck beyond it. Its saddle features shades of blue and green. The central camel is

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blue in hue and has two humps. Black stripes elongating from its head to its neck accentuate it. Its saddle is colored in shades of red and green. The saddle's geometric S and C fold decorations are visible. The red dromedary camel is located on the right. His neck is adorned with a broad golden strip that draws attention. The body also has a golden strip. His saddle is adorned with shades of gray and green. The camel figures' embellishments and the arrangement as a whole indicate that this picture depicts a wedding celebration, a military triumph, etc.

Photo 1: Ceramic Jug with Minai Technique, David SamlingMuseum

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The piece is a minai-made plate with a spherical body and a high ring base that features an image of Azade and Behram Gûr. The plate's rim is surrounded by a black text band, and its outside is coated in an opaque white gloss. On a white background, the composition on the inside surface mostly uses shades of green, red, black, brown, and light gray.

The inner surface of the lip is surrounded by a gray, wavy band. Just below it, a strip of gray-green-toned Kufic lettering, surrounded by a red line on top and bottom, encircles the entire plate and repeats the "el-devle" script again.

A gray camel, Bahram Gur, and Azade are seated on a green saddle adorned with white flower designs in the middle of the plate. A person sitting cross-legged is seen on the right and left of the camel's top portion. In other images, these individuals must be the servants behind the camel. The gazelle figure that Behram Gur shot with his arrow is standing close to a tree in front of the camel. Between the camel and its front and rear are fruit trees with pomegranate-like plants. Below the camel's feet, at the bottom, is a picture of a lake including a fish, a water snake, and a duck or geese. A broad red line at the bottom and an upside-down horseshoe pattern, rumis, and numerous folds make up the two crown-like decorations, one to the left of the camel's head and the other to the top of Azade's head. To complete the perspective of nature, four bird figurines were sketched in the spaces left by their absence (Kayın, 2019:73).

Behram Gûr's clothing and the attendants seated on each side of him are both the same hue in the composition. The person on the right's outfit actually has the same white-on-gray spotty pattern as Behram's. The person seated on the left is decked up in a gray dress with white Rumi patterns. Every human figure in the composition, with the exception of the one on the left, has a halo around their heads. Behram Gûr's white and occasionally crimson niello, adorned with plants, is slung from his left side. It shows Bahram pulling out his bow and releasing his arrow. One of the gazelle's ears and its rear leg are also shown to be held in place by an arrow.

Unlike in earlier works, Azade is shown in this example with darker complexion and without an emphasis on attractiveness. The person sitting atop the camel with its body looking backwards is hidden by its covered legs. He swivels his head to face Behram, who is firing

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arrows. It appears like he is of a different race and intended to highlight slavery because of his big, arched nose, slanted eyes that are stretched to the sides, and unusual mouth and chin shape. He's dressed in something with a crimson base and a white floral design. The figure is shown playing the ceng with both hands on it.

*Photo 2 : Ceramic plate with Minai technique depicting Behram Gur and Azade ,
Metropolitan Museum*

The left hand's thumb and index finger movements on the ceng strings were highlighted in particular (Kayın, 2019:74).

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The piece is a spherical-bodied plate created using the minai method, on the inside of which are images of Behram Gur and Azade. Around the edge of the plate is a strip of Kufi writing in shades of green, red, and pale blue. The whole base of the plate is covered in a white, gilded arrangement of rumi, varied leaves, and branches. Bahram Gur and Azade are seen in the middle of the plate, seated atop a gray, two-humped camel and wearing a turquoise saddle adorned with gold plant patterns. Six bands of various shades of reddish brown, both with and without rattles, round the camel's neck from head to toe. Two persons are seen sitting cross-legged behind the camel, and based on their gestures with their hands and arms, it appears like they are conversing. Given the other cases we have on the same issue, these statistics have to be servant figures. Their clothing is adorned with greenery, with gray on the left and crimson on the right. Draws attention is a belt with a tassel at the end that flies from the figure's headpiece on the right to her left. Unlike the representations in previous works on the same topic, Behram Gûr has not yet photographed the running animal figure in front of the camel. Although this animal is frequently shown as a gazelle, another species is observed in this instance (Kayın, 2019:76).

It shows Bahram Gûr pulling out his bow and releasing his arrow. But there isn't an arrow in this illustration. Behram Gûr is dressed in a light blue gown with a headpiece in shades of blue and green with gilded flower motifs. His head is surrounded by a reddish-brown halo. On his left side dangles a blue quiver devoid of any design.

Azade is dressed in a turquoise gown with golden accents. He has a gilt tiraz fastened to his dress's right sleeve. When playing the çeng, the dress's right sleeve, which stretches toward the wrist, drops down, revealing the golden interior lining of the garment. Azade's hair is long and straight, black, and she wears a cobalt blue hat. Azade and the attendants aren't enchanted here. With her back to Behram, Azade is seated behind him. Kayın (2019:77) states that the person pictured playing the chang can only be seen with its right hand on the strings.

Photo 3: Ceramic plate depicting Behram Gur and Azade, Art Gallery of South Australia

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The piece is a minai-made plate with a conical body and a high ring base that features a picture of Azade and Behram Gûr in the center. A blue Kufic script band with white outlines on a red backdrop with interwoven patterns and opaque white glaze encircles the outside of the vase.

The mouth is surrounded by a Kufi script band made in blue with red outlines on a black backdrop of vegetation. Ten mounted figures are arranged side by side underneath it, and one standing figure is seen around the plate's body. The band containing these figures is separated from the composition in the middle by a border made up of triangles and diamond slices stacked one over the other and side by side in the hues blue, green, red, and yellow.

The image of Bahram Gur and Azade is located in the plate's middle. Behram Gûr and Azade are depicted in the composition's center, perched on a blue saddle atop a black, double-humped camel with a blue bell dangling around its neck. The composition is fashioned on a bright yellow backdrop. Two figures of gazelles stand in front of the camel; one is bleeding from an arrow wound, while the other is fleeing. The gazelle that is running away is yellow, but the one that was shot was blue. The image of Azade, crushed by the camel that Behram rode on, is seen beneath the foot of the camel. Azade's long, straight black hair is covered with a crimson hat and a blue outfit with a water drop design. Thin, curving branches brimming with blue and scarlet flowers were employed throughout the piece to occupy empty space and evoke a sense of the natural world. Two further bird figures were added to the composition: one stood in front of Behram's bow, and the other stood between the blue gazelle and Azade, who was resting on the ground. The image of Behram Gûr shows him pulling out his bow and aiming his arrow at a gazelle. He is dressed in something akin to a robe that is embroidered with flowers. Behram Gûr is shown as having short black hair, a mustache, a beard, and a blue hat on his head (Kayın, 2019:80).

Azade wore gold pants underneath her olive-green ensemble. Her waist-length, straight, black hair falls to her shoulders, and a brown hat covers her head. He features almond eyes, big cheeks, a petite mouth, and eyebrows that resemble bows. One may argue that this image of

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Azade has a Seljuk face type and is rendered in line with the notion of beauty prevalent at the time. Seated just behind Behram Gûr, Azade raises her upper body and plays the çeng in reverse.

Photo 4: Minai technique plate , MetropolitanMuseum

Photo 5: Minai technique plate detail , MetropolitanMuseum

The piece is a plate with a conical body and a high ring base that was created using the minai method. The plate's rim is surrounded by a blue border, and its outside is covered in an opaque white finish. The interior surface has a border painted in alternate tones of turquoise, red, and pale grey, encircling the lip in two red stripes and separated into rectangular portions.

Two camels in turquoise and light gray hues stand in the center of the plate, and there are cross-legged individuals positioned above the camels on the right and left. In other images, these individuals must be the servants behind the camel. Additionally, a pine tree splits the plate in half evenly. The pine tree's upper portion is striped in black and turquoise, while the trunk is red. At the base of the tree is a decorative element made up of white and gray lines. The plate's empty spaces are embellished with greenery that resembles a crimson pomegranate design.

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The camel with two humps on the right is the pale gray-toned one in the middle of the group of camels. Black lines accentuate its left foreleg and neck. He wears a saddle that combines crimson and turquoise. The saddle has no decorative elements.

Cross-legged, the individual on the upper right is seated. He's dressed in red and white striped clothing. The figure's hair is blunt and black, with no distinguishing facial characteristics. He wears a gray headgear and a head halo. Cross-legged, the other person is seated. He's dressed in striped gray and white clothing. This figure's face characteristics are not as distinct as those of the other model. The figure has harsh black hair. On his head, there is a halo.

The turquoise-colored camel with two humps is located on the left side of the plate. There are black stripes on the head, throat, and forelegs. He's wearing a gray saddle. There is a red stripe detail on the saddle.

Photo 6: Minai technique ceramic plate, Victoria and Albert Museum

Photo 7: Ceramic plate detail with minai technique , Victoria and Albert Museum

The piece is created using the molding and embossing process, and its glaze is turquoise and its paste is white. The central figure is the camel carrying a palanquin. Standing on a rectangular plate, the camel-like creature has a broad neck and short, thick legs. The relief technique draws attention to the camel's head and neck. The palanquin, or two-humped camel, is supported by three legs on each side and has a pyramid-shaped body on its back.

The palanquin features two lion figurines on top and is constructed using openwork method. Not a single lion has lived to this day. The heads of the three individuals seated on either side of the camel are in contact with the palanquin's legs. These figurines are shown in a symmetrical arrangement. The figurines' diminutive size and distortion make it impossible to see their details. The characters are reported to be standing with their hands up in the air.

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Although Grube notes that it is challenging to draw clear conclusions about the workshop where pieces such as these were created, he speculates that they could have been created in Rey to cater to the specialized preferences of the palace nobility (Grube, 1965:219).

The lion image is a Seljuk sign for the Sun (Light) and for sovereignty (Strength and Power). Depending on the context, the lion can represent the Sun sign in astrology, a coat of arms, or a protective animal (Erginsoy, 1978:129).

Photo 8: Single color with molding technique Photo 9: With molding technique

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Turquoise Glazed Figurine, Pergamonmuseum Single Color Turquoise Glazed Figurine

Detail

Photo 10: Standing camel figure with luster technique , Islamic art London

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The sculpture is created utilizing the molding method and white paste. It has an opaque white glaze and is embellished with luster technique. The camel, which is standing on its feet and carrying a vase on its back, is the primary figure. His legs are shown as being big and short.

The figure has an ornate composition that extends from its head to every part of its body. The medallions are filled with various botanical embellishments. A halter that stretches from the camel's neck to the vase's body is located on its left side.

The camel's body narrows towards a large mouth, and it has a vase on its back that is supported by three legs on either side. Two little vases with floral decorations are positioned on either side of the vase's body. On the camel's body, the identical vases were arranged in pairs. This composition reached a progressive cohesiveness. There are two distinct decorative elements on the vase's body. At the bottom is a curving branch-based herbal design. Medallions on the upper torso are adorned with a variety of herbal designs. The central medallion features two individuals seated cross-legged. Their attire is golden. The figures' facial characteristics are incomprehensible. The vase's neck is adorned with ornaments as well. On the neck area, sequential deformities are seen. It seems to me that it may have been used to fill the vase with water or fragrance.

Photo 11: Detail of a standing camel figure with luster technique , Islamic art London

Photo 12: Detail of a standing camel figure with luster technique , Islamic art London

EVALUATION

Every civilization's visual arts have a rich history of figural expression. Beginning with the images of people carved into rocks in caves, the demand for visual expression has grown along with human civilization and persisted until the present day. Through this process, the

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iconographic compositions that the figures have assembled seem to be an object's way of transferring both real and imagined expressions.

The theme, the setting depicted, and the composition of the pieces in the article "Camel Figure in Seljuk Period Ceramic Art" were assessed in terms of material and technique.

Subject

The works in the catalog were examined in three groups according to their subjects: hunting, migration and ceremony. A classification of hunting-themed works according to their subjects

It has not been done. This is because; All eight works discussed were staged on the same subject. This

The main characters in the scene are Behram Gur and Azade. On a camel chasing prey

Behram Gur is always in a position where he leans forward and draws his bow. If Azade

He is depicted sitting on the opposite side of Behram Gur and playing the harp in his hand. If the place is

It is always a land decorated with plants (Photo: 2,3,4).

A campaign scene is reflected in migration-themed works. The main character is a camel. And the composition takes place around the camel (Photo: 6).

The works we consider as ceremonial scenes appear in two types. In the first one, the camel figure is directly involved in the event. This incident is; They are interpreted as scenes depicting a bride-taking or military victory of the period. In the other, the artifacts appear as details of belongings belonging to a palace family and used on special occasions (Photo: 1,8,10)

Type of Scene and Composition

Upon scrutinizing the samples with camel imagery found in the library, three distinct scenario types surfaced: hunting, ceremonial, and migration. Three of the seven pieces we looked at have to do with hunting, three with ceremonial, and one with migration as the central topic. On a ceramic plate using the minai method, only three pieces with a hunting motif are seen (Photo: 2,3,4). One of the three ceremonial-themed pieces is painted using minai technique on the body of a ceramic jug (Photo: 1). Two further pieces are available; one is a figure created using the luster process (Photo: 10) and the other features a single-color glazed figure (Photo: 8). The sole piece featuring a migratory motif is illustrated using the minai method on a ceramic plate (Photo: 6).

The compositions with hunting themes are all the same. This composition has a man and a woman throwing arrows at a camel in the middle, surrounded by one or more individuals (Photo: 2,3,4). Two categories were used to assess works with a ceremonial subject. In the first group, a packed area was set up, with a camel at the center and a row of camels arranged like a dish or bowl (Photo: 1). The figures in the second group are compositions. On his back, each of them is carrying a vase or palanquin (Photo: 8,10). On the other hand, pieces with a migration theme assembled into a dish or bowl, with a camel at the center and surrounding natural scenery (Photo: 6).

Material and Technique

The catalogue looked at seven works in total. In the context of this publishing research, only one item was looked at. The catalog has seven ceramic pieces, which include two figures (Photos 8–12), one jug (Photo: 1), and four plates (Photos 2-7).

Ceramic materials provide for a wide range of color and decorating options by nature. Therefore, the richness of ceramic works is noteworthy not only in terms of this range of shapes but also in terms of construction and decorating techniques as well as colors employed (Kayın,

2019:447). These pieces employ single-color glazing and mineral decoration methods. In addition to this, it has been noted that the works were also shaped using the mold shaping and embossing techniques.

On a white backdrop, the four plate group examples are embellished using the minai method. A single color glaze and mold relief adorn one of the jugs, minai, and two figurines among the other ceramic pieces, while luster adorns the other figure.

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